

EFFECT OF PLANTING DATES ON THE GROWTH AND MATURITY OF COWPEA IN THE GUINEA SAVANNAH AGROECOLOGY OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The study determined the effect of planting dates on the growth and maturity of six improved cowpea varieties in three locations (Makurdi, Abuja and Zaria) and three cropping seasons (2016-2018) within Nigeria's Guinea Savanna agro-ecological zone. The experiment was laid in a split plot design with planting dates as the main plot and varieties as subplots, with three replications per treatment. Data were analyzed using SAS (SAS Institute, 2003) software. Planting dates affected the growth and maturity of cowpeas in the three seasons. The variety IT89KD-288 expressed higher growth and fodder yields in the early season. Photoperiod sensitive and late maturing varieties like IT89KD-288 should be planted around 22nd August in any of the locations while day-neutral and early to medium maturing varieties like UAM09-1055-6, IT99K-573-1-1, IT99K-573-2-1, UAM09-1051-1 and UAM09-1046-6-1 varieties can be planted between 15th-29th August for maximum productivity. A significant variety-by-environment interaction effect was detected for early-maturity varieties. UAM09-1046-6, UAM09-1051-1 and IT99K-573-2-1 varieties were identified as ideal for early maturity in all locations. The selected varieties are recommended for production in Guinea Savannah or in similar agro-ecologies and for incorporation in future production and breeding programs targeting genetic improvement for grain yield.

Key words: Cowpea production, Improved varieties, Planting date, Location, Season

INTRODUCTION

In general, climate change has caused significant modification of cropping seasons in different regions, and the effect of this alteration is variation in the performance of crop species grown in different environments (Lobell *et al.*, 2008). The shift in rainfall pattern due to

climate change affects the intensity and frequency of rainfall, and this has a direct effect on the productivity of the crops. The shift in planting dates also implies that some crops that have been traditionally cultivated by the farmers may no longer be suited to the new season durations. As such, there is also a need to diversify the

crop base utilized by subsistence farmers as an effort to increase on-farm agro-biodiversity and resilience. Strategies to achieve this should also pay attention to challenges of food and nutritional insecurity that persist in rural households.

The choice of planting dates could significantly impact on growth and yields of crops, particularly during the critical development phases where plants require adequate moisture and ideal temperatures at planting, seedling establishment, flowering and fruit formation. Poor planting date selection may subject crops to water and heat stress during dry spells at critical growth stages resulting in reduced yield. In order to minimize farming risk, a need arises to ascertain planting dates and good crop choices among subsistence farmers (Mojaddam and Nouri, 2014).

In Nigeria cowpea is majorly produced in the savannah belt. Its yield in the Guinea Savannah is influenced by some environmental factors including rainfall, hence it is seasonal. Identification of appropriate time of planting a crop in a particular location is thus an important agronomic requirement needed for high and sustained productivity. Alteration of planting dates has been reported by many researchers as effective strategies for reducing pest damage (Ekesi *et al.*, 1996; Karungi *et al.*, 2000). Akande (2007) reported the effects of year, locations, planting dates and climatic factors on crop production, particularly legume crops. This has prompted the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) to engage in the development of varieties possessing diverse combinations of plant type, different maturity periods and resistance to several diseases, insect pests, and parasitic weeds in addition to possessing good agronomic traits. Subjecting these newly developed improved cowpea varieties to multi-environmental trials will help to identify

superior and stable cowpea varieties as well as understand the effect of variety and environment on cowpea performance. It is against this background that the current study was initiated to evaluate six varieties of cowpea in the Guinea Savannah agro-ecological environment, with a view to selecting the varieties that adapt to the conditions of this agricultural zone using Makurdi, Abuja and Zaria environments as case study. Variation in the performance of crop species grown in these environments at different planting dates will result to significant modifications of cropping seasons that will help farmers adapt their farming methods and mitigate the impact of climate change on cowpea production. The aim of this study therefore was to determine the effects of planting dates on the growth and maturity of cowpea.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Sites

The study was conducted at three locations; Makurdi, Abuja and Zaria in 2016, 2017 and 2018 cropping seasons. The three locations are within the Guinea Savanna agro-ecological zone of Nigeria, considered as non-traditional cowpea growing region. At Makurdi, the experimental field was located at the Teaching and Research Farm of the College of Agronomy (7.41°N, 8.37°E, 97m a.s.l.), IITA/IAR Teaching and Research Farm, Samaru, Zaria (11.086° N, 7.719° E, 675 m a.s.l) and IITA Teaching and Research Farm, Kubwa, Abuja (9.076° N, 7.399° E, 476m a.s.l). All three locations in the Guinea Savanna ecological zone are characterized by an annual rainfall of 1000 to 1500 mm. The soil type in the locations is Alfisols on Argillaceous sediments (Kwari *et al.*, 1999). Field trials were conducted during the growing seasons of 2016, 2017 and 2018 at Abuja, Makurdi and Zaria, under the rainfed condition. Meteorological data were

collected from the three locations for the three years of study.

Meteorological Data

Rainfall was distributed through out the rainy season in Abuja having recorded high frequency in August and September followed by four months dry season (January, February, November and December). The maximum temperature value recorded was 38.2 in February 2006 while sunshine lasted for a maximum of 25 hours in March 2007 (International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, Abuja Weather Station). Makurdi experienced the highest rainfall in September (268.9mm) in 2016 season. In the sequent season, rainfall pattern was highest in August (Nigerian Meteorological Agency, Headquarters, Tactical Air Command, Makurdi-Airport). Zaria location is characterized by high frequency of rainfall and humidity between July and September. Maximum temperature readings were in the range of 28.0-35.8 in 2016; 28.8-38.1 in 2017 and 27.8- 37.1 in 2018 (International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Samaru Zaria Weather Sub-Station, Kaduna)

Preliminary Soil Analysis

The soil of the experimental sites was sampled randomly with soil auger, borings in four places to a depth of 0-15 cm. The soil samples were bulked, air-dried and sieved through 2mm sieve before physical and chemical analysis was carried out in the Soil Science Laboratory of the Department of Soil Science, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria. Physicochemical parameters were assessed following standard procedures (Page *et al.*, 1982).

Plant Materials and Planting Seasons

Each year, six improved cowpea varieties (IT99K-573-1-1, IT99K-573-2-1, IT89KD-288, UAM09-1055-6, UAM09-

1046-6-1, and UAM09- 1051-1.) were used for the study. They were obtained from the International Institute for Tropical Agriculture (IITA) Kano Station and the Breeding Unit of the Molecular Biology Laboratory, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

Experimental Design and Pre-planting Field Activities

The experiment was laid out in split plot design with planting dates as main plot and varieties as subplots, with three replications per treatment. The plot size for each treatment comprised four rows of 5m length, spaced 0.75m row apart to give a gross plot size of 15m². Three seeds were planted per hill at 25 cm spacing between plants and thinned to two, 2 weeks after seedling emergence, providing a uniform plant population of about 106,667 plants ha⁻¹. Recommended fertilizer rate of 30 kg/ha P₂O₅ in the form of single super phosphate was applied at planting. The experimental fields at each location were ploughed, harrowed with a tractor twice to a fine tilth and thereafter, ridges were also made with tractor.

Seed Sowing and Post-planting Activities

The seeds of the cowpea varieties were treated with Apron Star 42 WS containing Metalaxyl-M 20% w/w, Difenconazole 2% w/w and Thiamethoxam 20% w/w at the rate of one sachet (10g) to 8kg of seeds for protection against soil and seed-borne pests and diseases. Seeds were planted for four planting dates (15th August, 22nd August, 29th August, and 5th September) across the three locations. Sowing was done manually; three seeds were sown per hole and later thinned to two seedlings per hill at fourteen (14) days after sowing (DAS). Weeds were controlled with Pendilin (500g pendimethalin per litre as an emulsifiable concentrate) at the rate of 100 mls in 20 litres of water Knapsack

sprayer (2L/Ha) and applied immediately after planting.

Data Collection and Analysis

Data were collected from 5 selected plants of the net plot. Growth parameters included plant height (cm) at 8 weeks after planting and number of branches per plant at physiological maturity. Number of days to maturity was taken as the number of days from planting to the day when 95 percent of the pods had dried (Pandey and Ngarm, 1985). All data were analyzed using SAS (SAS Institute, 2003) procedure and Standard Error was used to separate the treatment means.

RESULTS

Soil Physicochemical Properties

The physicochemical properties of soil samples of the experimental sites are presented in Table 1. The textural class consisted of sandy loam at Makurdi, clay

loam at Zaria and loamy soil at Abuja locations. Soils were slightly acidic ($\text{pH} < 7$) but high in organic carbon ($7.7 - 10.7 \text{ g kg}^{-1}$), nitrogen ($0.02 - 0.05 \%$) and phosphorus ($4.5 - 15.7 \text{ mg kg}^{-1}$) suitable for cowpea cultivation.

Multifactorial Effects of Measured Traits on Cowpea

Analysis of variance in the three experimental sites (table 2) showed significant effects of location (L), Year (Y), Planting date (PD) and Variety (V) on the growth parameters (height and branches). Only the Variety factor also affected both flowerig and maturity of the crop ($p < 0.05$), although Location factor affected day to 95% maturity. Among the sources of variation, only the interactions of Location x Variety, Location x Year x Variety and Planting date x Variety had significant effects ($p < 0.05$) on all growth and maturity traits evaluated

Table 1: Soil Properties at Experimental Fields prior to Planting

Soil Composition	Locations			Method of Analysis
	Makurdi	Abuja	Zaria	
Physical Properties				Hydrometer Method
Sand (%)	77.6	70	70	Hydrometer Method
Silt (%)	13.2	7	12	Hydrometer Method
Clay (%)	9.2	13	18	Hydrometer Method
Textural class	Sandy loamy	Loamy	Clay loam	
Chemical Properties				
pH (H ₂ O) 1:2.5	5.90	5.28	5.50	PH meter
pH (0.01M CaCl ₂) 1:2.5	4.60	4.40	5.80	PH meter
Organic carbon (g kg^{-1})	10.7	10.7	7.70	Walky-Black
Nitrogen (%)	0.05	0.015	0.04	spectrophotometric method
Bray P (mg kg^{-1})	7.61	15.74	4.48	Kjeldahl procedure

Table 2: Effects of Sources of Variation on Cowpea Varieties

Source	Plant height (cm)	Branches /m-2	Days to 95% Maturity
Location (L)	<.0001	0.0042	<.0001
Year (Y)	0.0009	<.0001	<.0001
L x Y	<.0001	0.1593	<.0001
Planting date (PD)	0.0127	<.0001	0.6212
L x PD	0.9310	0.0825	0.4245
Y x PD	0.5146	0.0247	0.6212
L x Y x PD	0.8120	0.2434	0.4724
Variety (V)	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001
L x V	<.0001	<.0001	<.0001
Y x V	<.0001	<.0001	0.1942
L x Y x V	<.0001	0.0009	0.0015
PD x V	0.0002	<.0001	<.0001
L x PD x V	0.9998	0.9508	0.1459
Y x PD x V	0.4999	0.8796	0.9979
L x Y x PD x V	1.0000	0.0229	0.9962

Effects of Planting dates on the growth and maturity of cowpea in Abuja Location in three seasons

Effect on growth traits

In Abuja location, plant height varied significantly with planting date (PD) as given in Table 3. In 2016 season, height performance ranged from 51.4 at PD4 to 54.1cm at PD1. IT99K-573-2-1 (54.5cm) and UAM09-1055-6 (54.7cm) varieties planted at PD1 had the tallest heights

while PD2 performed best in IT99K-573-1-1 (51cm), IT89KD-288 (69cm) and UAM09-1051-1 (45.7cm). UAM09-1046-6-1 recorded the tallest height at PD 3 (55.5cm). in the 2017 season, crops with PD1 gave the shortest height (48cm) while those with higher PDs had taller heights. Results showed that PD4 performed best in three varieties including IT99K-573-1-1 (49.1cm), IT89KD-288 (49.9cm) and UAM09-1046-6-1 (50.7cm) while PD3 influenced the growth of UAM09-1051-1

with 53cm in height. IT99K-573-2-1 and UAM09-1055-6 had the tallest heights at PD2 with 61.7cm and 52.9cm respectively. In the 2018 cropping season, crops with PD2 were the tallest on the average as shown in IT99K-573-1-1 (57.3cm), IT99K-573-2-1 (61.7cm) and UAM09-1055-6 (52.9cm) while crops planted at PD3 and PD4 had the tallest heights in UAM09-1046-6-1 and UAM09-1051-1.

Number of branches varied significantly with planting date (PD) as given in Table 4. In the 2016 cropping season, plants with PD2 produced more branches (26.9) than other PDs on the average as recorded in IT99K-573-1-1 (31.3 branches), UAM09-1046-6-1 (33.1 branches) and UAM09-1055-6 (19.3 branches). Other varieties performed best in branching at different planting dates including UAM14-1051-1 (29.8 branches at PD1), IT99K-573-2-1 (26.4 branches at PD3) and IT89KD-288 (32.7 branches at PD4). In the 2017 season,

PD1 and PD3 influenced branching with average of 31.6 and 31.1 branches respectively. IT99K-573-2-1, IT89KD-288 and UAM09-1055-6 produced the highest number of branches in PD1 while IT99K-573-1-1, UAM09-1046-6-1 and UAM14-1051-1 performed best in branching at PD3. In the 2018 season, similar results were obtained where PD1 and PD3 significantly influenced branching in the same varieties reported in the previous season.

Effects on 95% maturity

Planting date (PD) had no significant effects on days to 95% maturity of the crop, taking place between 70 and 72 days in the PDs (table 5) in the three cropping seasons. However, significant varietal differences were observed. IT99K-573-2-1, IT99K-573-1-1 and UAM09-1055-6 were early maturing varieties (60-62 days) while IT89KD-288 was a late maturing variety (91-93 days)

Table 3: Effect of Planting Date (PD) on Plant Height (cm) of Some Cowpea Varieties at Abuja in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018						
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean
	Plant height (cm)														
IT99K-573-1-1	50.1	51.0	49.0	48.4	49.6	44.9	46.3	45.7	49.1	46.5	50.0	57.3	45.0	49.1	50.4
IT99K-573-2-1	54.5	50.7	51.8	51.7	52.2	47.8	61.7	51.3	52.7	53.4	47.8	61.7	51.3	52.7	53.4
IT89KD-288	67.0	69.0	65.0	63.6	66.2	48.3	49.2	48.9	49.9	49.1	53.3	51.0	45.7	49.3	49.8
UAM09-1046-6-1	54.3	54.8	55.5	53.3	54.5	47.7	46.9	50.1	50.7	48.8	47.7	47.5	50.7	50.7	49.2
UAM09-1051-1	44.1	45.7	43.1	42.0	43.7	49.3	48.3	53.0	50.0	50.2	49.3	48.3	53.0	50.0	50.2
UAM09-1055-6	54.7	52.1	52.1	49.6	52.1	49.7	52.9	51.5	47.9	50.5	49.7	52.9	51.8	47.9	50.5
Mean	54.1	53.9	52.7	51.4	51.4	48.0	50.9	50.1	50.1	50.1	49.6	53.1	49.6	50.0	50.5

Table 4: Effect of Planting Dates on Number of Branches of Some Cowpea Varieties at Abuja in 2016, 2017 and 2018 Cropping Seasons

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018						
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean
	Number of Branches/m ²														
IT99K-573-1-1	20.0	31.3	28.0	23.1	25.6	29.6	30.2	31.3	24.4	28.9	29.6	30.2	31.3	24.4	28.9
IT99K-573-2-1	23.8	19.3	26.4	22.4	23.0	29.1	23.1	24.9	22.7	24.9	29.1	23.1	24.9	22.7	24.9
IT89KD-288	27.1	30.4	30.9	32.7	30.3	46.9	35.1	36.4	24.4	35.7	46.9	35.1	36.4	24.4	35.7
UAM09-1046-6-1	24.2	33.1	30.9	29.1	29.3	23.8	28.7	36.7	28.2	29.3	23.8	28.7	36.2	28.2	29.2
UAM14-1051-1	29.8	28.0	23.8	24.7	26.6	31.8	32.7	34.0	26.2	31.2	31.8	32.7	34.0	26.2	31.2
UAM09-1055-6	12.9	19.3	16.9	11.1	15.1	28.4	17.1	23.6	25.1	23.6	28.4	17.1	23.6	25.1	23.6
Mean	23.0	26.9	26.1	23.8	23.8	31.6	27.8	31.1	25.2	23.6	31.6	27.8	31.1	25.2	23.6

Table 5: Effect of Planting Dates (PD) on Days to 95% Maturity of Some Cowpea Varieties at Abuja in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018						
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean
	Days to 95% maturity														
IT99K-573-1-1	63.0	61.0	61.7	62.7	62.1	62.0	60.3	60.7	61.3	61.1	62.0	60.3	60.7	61.3	61.1
IT99K-573-2-1	62.7	61.0	62.0	60.7	61.6	60.0	60.7	61.0	60.0	60.4	60.0	60.7	61.0	60.0	60.4
IT89KD-288	95.3	92.0	89.7	93.3	92.6	94.0	91.7	89.7	90.3	91.4	94.0	91.7	89.7	90.3	91.4
UAM09-1046-6-1	75.7	73.7	75.0	75.7	75.0	74.3	74.7	74.7	74.7	74.6	74.3	74.7	74.7	74.7	74.6
UAM09-1051-1	73.0	72.3	74.0	73.7	73.2	74.7	74.7	75.0	73.7	74.5	74.7	74.7	75.0	73.7	74.5
UAM09-1055-6	60.0	62.3	61.0	64.7	62.0	60.7	62.0	61.3	64.7	62.2	60.7	62.0	61.3	64.7	62.2
Mean	71.6	70.4	70.6	71.8	70.9	70.9	70.7	70.4	70.8	70.8	70.9	70.7	70.4	70.8	70.8

Effects of Planting dates on the growth and maturity of cowpea in Makurdi Location in three seasons

Effect on growth traits

In Makurdi location, plant height varied significantly with planting date (PD) as given in Table 6. In the 2016 season, height performance ranged from 46.9cm at PD4 to 49.0 cm at PD2. All varieties grew taller at PD2 than other PDs except UAM09-1051-1 in PD4 (41.9cm). In the 2017 season, crops with PD1 and PD2 were the tallest in height (54.3- 54.4cm) with significant differences in height at other PDs. Significant varietal differences were observed as IT89KD-288 had the tallest height while UAM09-1051-1 was the shortest in the first two season. In the 2018 cropping season, crops with PD2 were the tallest on the average (50.9cm). Variety IT99K-573-2-1 grew tall to 61.7cm at PD2 while those at PD1 were short in height.

The number of branches varied significantly with planting date (PD) and variety, as given in Table 7. In the 2016 cropping season, plants with PD1 produced more branches (26.9) than other PDs on the average as recorded in IT99K-573-1-1 (22.9 branches), IT89KD-288 (31.3 branches), UAM09-1051-1 (35.3 branches) and UAM09-1055-6 (8 branches). Meanwhile, IT99K-573-2-1 performed best at PD4 with 15.6 branches. In the 2017 season, PD2 positively influenced more branching with average of 30 branches per variety. Five of the six varieties had the highest number of branches in PD2. In the 2018 season, PD1 or PD3 significantly influenced branching at 50% of the varieties. PD1 assisted the branching pattern in IT99K-573-2-1 (29.1 branches), IT89KD-288 (46.9 branches) and UAM09-1055-6 (28.4 branches), PD3 was observable in IT99K-573-1-1 (33.6 branches), UAM09-1046-6-1 (36.7 branches) and UAM09-1051-1 (34

branches).

Effects on 95% maturity

Planting date (PD) had no significant effects on days to 95% maturity of the crop, taking place between 70 and 72 days (Table 8) in the three cropping seasons. However, significant varietal differences were observed. IT99K-573-2-1, IT99K-573-1-1 and UAM09-1055-6 were early maturing varieties (60-63 days) while IT89KD-288 was a late maturing variety (91-93 days). UAM09-1046-6-1 and UAM09-1051-1 were intermediate (73-75 days)

Effects of Planting dates on the growth and maturity of cowpea in Zaria Location in three seasons

Effect on growth traits

In Zaria location, plant height varied significantly with planting date (PD) only in the second and third planting seasons (Table 9). In the first season (2016), it ranged from 44.6cm at PD4 to 46.5 cm at PD2. Height differences were not significant along the planting dates but dependent on variety effect where IT89KD-288 was the tallest plants (61.1cm) while UAM09-1051-1 was the shortest (39.6cm). In the 2017 season, crops planted at PD2 (49.3cm) were the tallest on the average planting dates as recorded in IT99K-573-2-1 (59.9cm) and UAM09-1055-6 (51.3cm) whereas PD4 recorded the tallest plants in IT99K-573-1-1 (47.7cm), IT89KD-288 (48.8cm) and UAM09-1046-6-1(49.1cm). In the 2018 cropping season, crops with PD2 were the tallest on the average (53.4cm) as recorded in IT99K-573-2-1 (64.8cm) and UAM09-1055-6 (55.5cm). Some varieties planted at PD4 showcased tall heights including IT99K-573-1-1 (51.5cm), IT89KD-288 (52.4cm) and UAM09-1046-6-1 (53.2cm) while UAM09-1051-1 (55.5cm) was the tallest at Pd2.

Number of branches varied significantly with planting date (PD) and variety (Table 10). In the 2016 cropping season, plants with PD1 produced more branches (28) than other PDs as recorded in IT99K-573-2-1 (30 branches), IT89KD-288 (40 branches) and UAM09-1055-6 (24 branches). Similar trend was recorded in the 2017 season with slight differences. In the 2018 season, large number of branches were obtained from plants at PD3 (38 branches) where five out of the six varieties

produced the highest number of branches.

Effects on 95% maturity

Planting date (PD) had significant effects on days to 95% maturity of the crop in the three seasons, with significant variety effect (Table 11). PD4 contained early maturing varieties in the 2016 and 2018 seasons (86 and 75 days respectively) while PD1 contained early maturing varieties in 2017 seasons (72 days)

Table 6: Effect of Planting Dates on Plant Height (cm) of Some Cowpea Varieties at Makurdi in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018							
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	
	Plant height (cm)															
IT99K-573-1-1	43.9	44.5	43.5	42.4	43.6	50.2	54.3	49.0	51.4	51.2	44.9	47.8	48.7	47.7	49.3	49.7
IT99K-573-2-1	45.2	44.9	43.5	45.2	44.7	54.5	50.7	48.5	51.7	51.4	47.8	48.7	47.7	49.3	49.7	49.7
IT89KD-288	64.1	64.9	64.4	63.7	64.3	71.2	69.0	63.7	63.6	66.9	48.7	47.7	49.3	49.7	49.7	49.7
UAM09-1046-6-1	49.9	50.2	48.3	46.3	48.7	54.3	54.8	52.2	50.0	52.8	47.7	49.3	49.7	49.7	49.7	49.7
UAM09-1051-1	41.7	41.1	42.2	41.9	41.7	47.4	45.7	44.8	47.2	46.3	49.3	49.7	49.7	49.7	49.7	49.7
UAM09-1055-6	43.7	48.0	44.9	42.1	44.7	48.0	52.1	50.1	44.5	48.7	49.7	49.7	49.7	49.7	49.7	49.7
Mean	48.1	49.0	47.8	46.9	46.9	54.3	54.4	51.4	51.4	51.4	48.0	48.0	48.0	48.0	48.0	48.0

Table 7: Effect of Planting Dates on Number of Branches of Some Cowpea Varieties at Makurdi in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018							
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	
	Number of Branches/m ²															
IT99K-573-1-1	22.9	19.1	20.0	20.4	20.6	28.4	33.3	26.2	25.1	28.3	29.6	30.2	33.6	24.4	24.4	24.4
IT99K-573-2-1	15.1	14.0	12.2	15.6	14.2	24.7	27.8	27.1	21.6	25.3	29.1	23.1	24.9	22.7	22.7	22.7
IT89KD-288	31.3	27.3	28.7	28.4	28.9	28.2	29.3	29.3	32.7	29.9	46.9	35.1	36.4	24.4	24.4	24.4
UAM09-1046-6-1	25.1	24.4	28.7	24.7	25.7	21.1	33.1	32.9	29.3	29.1	23.8	28.7	36.7	28.2	28.2	28.2
UAM09-1051-1	35.3	26.4	31.6	27.3	30.2	31.1	30.4	26.2	25.1	28.2	31.8	32.7	34.0	26.2	26.2	26.2
UAM09-1055-6	8.0	6.9	6.0	6.0	6.7	18.4	25.8	18.4	12.4	18.8	28.4	17.1	23.6	25.1	25.1	25.1
Mean	23.0	19.7	21.2	20.4	20.4	25.3	30.0	26.7	24.4	24.4	31.6	27.8	31.5	25.2	25.2	25.2

Table 8: Effect of Planting Dates on Days to 95% Maturity of Some Cowpea Varieties at Makurdi in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018							
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	
	Days to 95% maturity															
IT99K-573-1-1	62.0	60.3	60.7	61.3	61.1	64.0	64.0	61.7	63.0	63.2	62.0	60.3	62.7	61.3	61.3	61.3
IT99K-573-2-1	60.0	60.7	61.0	60.0	60.4	65.7	61.7	62.7	60.7	62.7	61.0	60.7	61.0	60.0	60.0	60.0
IT89KD-288	94.0	91.7	89.7	90.3	91.4	95.7	93.7	91.3	88.7	92.3	94.3	91.7	89.7	90.3	90.3	90.3
UAM09-1046-6-1	74.3	74.7	74.7	74.7	74.6	75.7	74.3	75.0	75.0	75.0	74.3	74.7	74.7	74.7	74.7	74.7
UAM09-1051-1	74.7	74.7	75.0	73.7	74.5	73.7	72.3	74.0	73.7	73.4	74.7	74.7	75.0	73.7	73.7	73.7
UAM09-1055-6	60.7	62.0	61.3	64.7	62.2	61.7	62.3	61.7	64.0	62.4	60.7	62.0	61.3	64.7	64.7	64.7
Mean	70.9	70.7	70.4	70.8	70.8	72.7	71.4	71.1	70.8	70.8	71.2	70.7	70.7	70.8	70.8	70.8

Table 9: Effect of Planting Dates on Plant Height (cm) of Some Cowpea Varieties at Zaria in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018					
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4
	Plant height (cm)													
IT99K-573-1-1	41.7	42.3	41.3	40.3	41.4	43.6	44.9	44.4	47.7	45.1	47.1	48.5	48.0	51.5
IT99K-573-2-1	42.9	42.7	41.4	42.9	42.5	46.4	59.9	49.8	51.2	51.8	50.1	64.8	53.9	55.3
IT89KD-288	60.9	61.7	61.2	60.5	61.1	46.9	47.7	47.4	48.4	47.6	50.7	51.6	51.3	52.4
UAM09-1046-6-1	47.4	47.7	45.9	44.0	46.2	46.3	45.5	48.6	49.1	47.4	50.1	49.2	52.5	53.2
UAM09-1051-1	39.6	39.1	40.1	39.8	39.6	47.9	46.9	51.4	48.5	48.7	51.8	50.7	55.6	52.5
UAM09-1055-6	41.5	45.6	42.6	40.0	42.4	48.2	51.3	50.0	46.4	49.0	52.1	55.5	54.1	50.2
Mean	45.7	46.5	45.4	44.6	46.5	46.5	49.3	48.6	48.6	48.6	50.3	53.4	52.5	52.5

Table 10: Effect of Planting Dates (PD) on Number of Branches of Some Cowpea Varieties at Zaria in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018					
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4
	Number of Branches/ m ²													
IT99K-573-1-1	25.5	26.5	27.3	20.8	25.0	28.0	29.1	30.0	22.9	27.5	35.1	21.6	38.4	27.8
IT99K-573-2-1	29.9	23.8	21.0	20.2	23.7	32.9	26.2	23.1	22.2	26.1	30.9	22.7	46.0	26.0
IT89KD-288	40.4	31.3	32.9	20.8	31.4	44.4	34.4	36.2	22.9	34.5	30.4	21.1	42.4	23.6
UAM09-1046-6-1	20.6	25.1	32.3	24.2	25.6	22.7	27.6	35.6	26.7	28.1	34.4	27.1	36.2	26.9
UAM09-1051-1	28.3	28.9	29.7	23.2	27.5	31.1	31.8	32.7	25.6	30.3	30.2	26.0	31.8	19.6
UAM09-1055-6	24.0	14.3	21.0	22.2	20.4	26.4	15.8	23.1	24.4	22.4	38.7	23.6	33.1	28.7
Mean	28.1	25.0	27.4	21.9	27.5	30.9	27.5	30.1	24.1	24.1	33.3	23.7	38.0	25.4

Table 11: Effect of Planting Date (PD) on Days To 95% Maturity of Some Cowpea Varieties at Zaria in 2016, 2017 and 2018

Variety (V)	2016				2017				2018					
	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4	Mean	PD1	PD2	PD3	PD4
IT99K-573-1-1	84.7	84.7	85.0	83.3	84.4	69.7	78.7	77.7	75.0	75.2	79.7	75.0	75.2	79.7
IT99K-573-2-1	86.3	83.3	84.0	84.3	84.5	70.0	77.7	77.0	76.0	75.2	78.7	76.0	75.2	78.7
IT89KD-288	89.7	90.3	89.0	88.0	89.2	75.7	86.7	82.7	83.0	82.0	87.7	83.0	82.0	87.7
UAM09-1046-6-1	88.7	88.7	88.3	87.0	88.2	80.0	78.0	76.3	75.7	77.5	79.7	75.7	77.5	79.7
UAM09-1051-1	88.0	85.7	85.3	84.0	85.7	69.7	77.7	76.3	74.0	74.4	77.3	74.0	74.4	77.3
UAM09-1055-6	87.7	90.0	89.0	87.7	88.6	69.3	79.0	77.3	74.7	75.1	79.3	74.7	75.1	79.3
Mean	87.5	87.1	86.8	85.7	85.7	72.4	79.6	77.9	76.4	76.4	80.4	76.4	75.1	80.4

DISCUSSION

Results showed significant effects of location, year, planting date and variety on the growth parameters of cowpea. The results corroborate the findings of Ezeaku *et al.* (2015) who reported significant year or variety effects on growth and maturity of cowpea. In the present study, only the variety effect was observed to affect both flowerig and maturity of the crop, while location affected day to 95% maturity. Interactions of location x variety or location x year x variety or plantig date x variety had significant effects on growth, and maturity traits of cowpea. Results agrees with the findings of Akande (2007) and Shiringani, (2011) that reported significant interaction among the analyzed sources of variation. The variety by environment (GE) interactions plays a major role in the performance of any variety and in identification of adaptable varieties to varying environments. Interactions between variety and environment affect both quantitative and qualitative traits. This suggests varying effects of climate change and diverse ecological conditions in Nigeria. It also suggests the importance of selecting suitable varieties for adaptability to specific as well as across environments. Identification of the appropriate timing of sowing of a crop in any particular location is an important agronomic requirement needed for high and sustained productivity (Akande *et al.*, 2012). In all locations, planting dates affected growth parameters of cowpea in terms of heights and number of branches produced in the three seasons. However, there was no particular consistent pattern as different planting dates gave different results on plant growth depending on locations, seasons and varieties.

In the three planting seasons, all studied took a shorter period to attain 95% maturity when planted on 5th September, while August plantings (15th, 22nd and 29th)

resulted in the longest maturity periods. These results indicated that planting date was likely to have a significant effect on maturity period of cowpea and other growth parameters. Across all planting dates for both years, variety IT89KD-288 had the highest number of days to 95% maturity while UAM09- 1055-6 had the lowest number of days to maturity. Monitoring the maturity period of IT89KD-288 variety over a period of time was needed to confirm its response to day-length. This confirms the report of Akande *et al.* (2012) that cowpeas are short-day plants known to be sensitive to day-length, however, most of the recently improved varieties cultivated in Nigeria are day-length neutral and can be planted anytime of the year provided there is sufficient water, either through rainfall or irrigation. Fatokun *et al.* (2002) reported that delayed planting of early maturing varieties substantially delayed maturity, thereby reducing the chances of early harvest of the early planted and early maturing varieties. Similar report stated that early sowing can result in high grain yields if it enables the crop to escape hot summer weather that can hinder reproductive development (Hall, 1992). If sowing is too early, and soil temperature is cooler than 19°C, chilling damage can cause slow and incomplete emergence (Ismail *et al.*, 1997). The report concluded that cowpea varieties that begin maturity early can escape drought in some locations and years resulting high yields which is also in agreement with the current study.

In a similar vein, Mojaddam and Nouri (2014) reported that delay in sowing of cowpea decreased the length of vegetative and reproductive growth stages and reduce the grain yield of cowpea. Kamara *et al.* (2009) attributed the decrease in grain yield obtained in delayed sowing to the fact that plants' vegetative state faces intense heat of the season which resulted in decreased vegetative growth stage,

production of fewer vegetative organs, decreased assimilation, early maturity, increased in loss of flowers and infertility, and decrease in grain yield components in French bean. The significant differences in the growth and yield parameters of the varieties in response to planting dates could be attributed to the genetic differences in the various varieties studied. Determining the best sowing date for cowpea in the face of climate change with Variety and location specific information will secure Nigeria's relevance as one of the major producers of cowpea. The value of manipulating the planting date as a package for optimizing cowpea productivity has been confirmed in the current study, thus giving scientific credence to the traditional practice of planting early in the season than late planting.

C O N C L U S I O N A N D R E C O M M E N D A T I O N S

Planting dates affected growth and maturity of cowpea in the three seasons. This study has confirmed that the traditional planting date (September) used

by farmers in the study area is not delivering the potential productivity of cowpea. The variety IT89KD-288 expressed higher growth and fodder yields in early season, particularly in Makurdi and Abuja locations. It can therefore be recommended that photoperiod sensitive and late maturing varieties like IT89KD-288 should be planted around 22nd August and day-neutral and early to medium maturing varieties like UAM09-1055-6, IT99K- 573-1-1, IT99K-573-2-1, UAM09-1051-1 and UAM09-1046-6-1 varieties can be planted between 15th-29th August for maximum productivity. Significant variety-by-environment interaction effect was detected for early maturity among the test Varieties. Cowpea Varieties (UAM09-1046-6, UAM09-1051-1 and IT99K-573-2-1) were identified as ideal for early maturity. The selected cowpea varieties are recommended for production in Guinea Savannah, and for incorporation in future production and breeding programs targeting genetic improvement for grain yield.

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